

GEOPOLITICAL RAMIFICATIONS OF AI-DRIVEN SECURITY: ANALYTICAL STUDY OF ALPHABET, IBM, META AND MICROSOFT'S DIGITAL DEFENSE REPORTS 2024

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Abstract

Within the framework of digital sovereignty, this study examines the geopolitical implications of AI-supported cybersecurity, with a focus on the Digital Defense Reports released by Alphabet, IBM, Meta, and Microsoft in 2024. In parallel, the integration of AI in cybersecurity systems has become a strategic tool that influences the formulation of international power equations, as states are now more than ever craving to intervene in digital infrastructures. Tech giants are not only provide security solutions but also shape the global narrative around the defense of nations, data governance, and protection of critical infrastructure. Drawing from Geopolitical Theory (Kaplan, 2012) and Digital Sovereignty (Floridi, 2020), this research posits that in setting the framework for AI-enabled security technologies, there has been an attempt to influence the parameters of global competitiveness and collaborative policymaking. Document analysis and thematic coding using Atlas.ti 24 interrogate how these reports discursively position technological leadership and state-corporate interdependence. Findings point to corporate narratives reinforcing tightly-held strategic national agendas and revealing tension among innovation, regulation, and sovereignty within the changing landscape of global cybersecurity order. Stronger regulatory frameworks should be established by the policymakers to coherently align AI-derived cybersecurity with national interests of digital sovereignty.

INTRODUCTION

AI in cybersecurity is developing rapidly and has consequential geopolitical ramifications in an era increasingly defined by digital sovereignty. The AI-based cybersecurity solutions enhance threat detection and automatic responses in favor of national security. Yet, they also open up a whole new range of vulnerabilities, including algorithmic bias, adversarial threats, and data governance issues (Bharadiya, 2023; Ibekwe et al., 2024). With states

asserting control over their digital infrastructure, digital sovereignty becomes a crucial factor that continues to be defining in cybersecurity policymaking, shaping international relations, regulatory frameworks, and global market dynamics (Steinback, 2025). The research here explores AI-induced cybersecurity in relation to the geopolitical influence in the ongoing discourse on digital sovereignty. The actors in the technology industry

are critically examined, notably the governments, multinational corporations, and cybersecurity firms, using an analysis of white papers on strategic approaches to AI and cybersecurity governance. These industry papers present an opportunity to interrogate competing interests of global powers, tensions between state sovereignty and private sector influence, and models of digital governance differentiated by the European Union, China, and the BRICS + Alliance (Gromova & Ferreria, 2024).

While efforts to harmonize governance structures in both AI and cybersecurity continue, fragmentation in the global regulatory environment remains. The AI Act and Gaia-X initiative in the European Union aim at the creation of data- sovereignty frameworks that prioritize privacy and decentralized control; conversely, China's state-centered model emphasizes centralized control and AI-linked surveillance (Carrapico & Farrand, 2024). The 'contesting philosophies' inside this digital superpower geopolitical game exemplify the complex intersections of cybersecurity, technological autonomy, and other national-core security imperatives (Vagesna, 2023). The private sphere has now become an important actor in these battles concerning sovereignty, as corporations begin to use such measures as a way of resisting regulatory obstacles while pushing forward with AI-enabled security solutions (Carrapico & Farrand, 2024). This study extends an understanding of how AI-based security influences the order of the digital world. The presented research deals with how industry players view digital sovereignty, threats posed by AI-enabled security systems, and the strategic priorities associated with present-day cybersecurity governance. Thus the findings bring into sharper focus the larger debates on AI regulation and geopolitical rivalry and map digital sovereignty in the future of an AI-centric world.

This research also investigates the geopolitical implications of AI security in digital sovereignty by analyzing reports of worldwide technology companies. The study assesses how the interaction between the tech industry and AI governance affects identifying risks such as adversarial AI and regulatory discrepancies. Findings provide insight into how AI cybersecurity shapes global power structures, national security policies, and international cooperation. It

also stresses the need for harmonized regulations on AI to mitigate cybersecurity threats and foster ethical and transparent applications of AI in governance and security frameworks.

Literature Review

Confluence of artificial intelligence (AI) into cybersecurity redefines the geopolitical stage, more so within the construct of digital sovereignty. While AI threats detection, mechanism automation for response, and cyber resilience would constitute advances in cybersecurity, such innovations have also created new vulnerabilities, including algorithmic biases, data privacy issues, and adversarial AI threats (Bharadiya, 2023; Ibekwe et al., 2024). Both these aspects challenge national security strategies and necessitate strong governance frameworks to balance the two inevitable terms of innovation during regulation.

Digital sovereignty has therefore shifted from a traditional view of state control to one where data governance, cloud infrastructure, and self-sovereign identities come into view as concerned areas of strategic interest for global powers (Steinbach, 2024; Leong et al., 2021). The EU's AI Act and Gaia-X initiative are instances of reducing dependency on foreign tech giants while insisting on data localization laws (Carrapico & Farrand, 2024). On the other hand, the Chinese model is rather a state-controlled one emphasizing AI-driven surveillance and centralized control with two conflicting paradigms regarding digital sovereignty (Vegesna, 2023; Steinbach, 2024). The BRICS+ alliance brings up a contrasting approach that supports independent regulatory frameworks and sovereign cloud infrastructure to stand against Western technological dominance (Gromova & Ferreira, 2024).

Yet, notwithstanding those efforts, AI governance remains fragmented. The United States, the European Union, and China are advancing different narratives on AI policy, all of which contribute to governance gaps, the aggravation of which complicates the management of cybersecurity threats and international cooperation (Leong et al., 2021). Because the lack of harmonization is conducive to exploitation by adverse AI actors, questions arise regarding the role of multinationals with respect to global AI governance.

Cybersecurity harnessing AI is vital in peacekeeping, military operations and intelligence gathering, thus reinforcing the strategic dimensions of AI application. In predictive analytics for conflict prevention, the UN has explored AI, but military applications have voiced concerns regarding AI weaponization and autonomous decision-making in warfare (Pauwels, 2023). Increased use of AI for cybersecurity also poses the dangers of adversarial AI attacks, where machine-learning algorithms are deliberately compromised to bypass the defense mechanisms and penetrate critical infrastructure (Camaho, 2024). Governments and policy-makers now have to navigate these geopolitical tensions: uncertainty around data privacy, fresh threats of misinformation campaigns, and the protection of digital rights. While decentralized AI-governance presents an avenue toward legitimate cybersecurity policies founded on transparency and inclusivity, arguably, this avenue is hindered by private-sector influence-complexities set into motion especially by big tech companies-interfering with regulatory enforcement (Carrapico & Farrand, 2024).

Digital defense reports, in their consideration of AI-driven cybersecurity, constitute one of the vital conduits to shape and influence the international policy discourse landscape. White papers, which are ultimately released by powerful technology companies and policy institutions, take the lead in constructing narratives around AI regulatory considerations together with security frameworks and models for digital sovereignty (Robles-Carrillo, 2023; Fratini et al, 2024), they shed light on corporate perspectives in statesmanship while potentially revealing clashes with public interest considerations or national security concerns versus corporate agenda. Reviewing especially these white papers assists in unmasking existing power relationships that underpin AI-powered cybersecurity governance and thus achieve a critical reflection on the policy recommendation environment put forth by the private sector. AI has impacted cyberspace whereby its concerns rather on technical security aspects extend to those of geopolitical strategy and regulate sovereignty. The future of digital sovereignty will rest on the friction between state-governed sovereignty, multinational tech influence, and emergent global frameworks for AI. This paper examines the

relevance of the tech industry digital defense reports in order to provide a new understanding of how AI-governance narratives have been constructed, while simultaneously pinpointing gaps in policy and opportunities for equitable frameworks of AI-driven cybersecurity.

Geopolitical theory, digital sovereignty theory, and innovation system theory comprise the multidimensional theoretical approach on which the study rests. These frameworks provide a fit to analyze AI-driven cybersecurity with serious consequences for the exercise and distribution of global power, national governance regimes, and technological innovation. Whereas AI-driven cybersecurity intersects with geopolitical theory, digital sovereignty, and innovation systems theory-the synergy of such perspectives provides a comprehensive lens to understand the global dynamics surrounding AI technology. Geopolitical theory as propounded by Kaplan (2012)-analyzing AI-driven cybersecurity as a strategic asset-would suggest that nations utilize AIs for national security, military, and intelligence purposes so as to leverage control over the structures of global security. More and more countries are tending to use AI in cybersecurity as a way of ensuring geopolitical dominance; the US, EU, and China have pursued different models of digital sovereignty to control their digital infrastructures and protect their interests. These strategies include concepts of international trade policy, cyber security frameworks, and global governance architectures. In this arena, however, multinational technology firms play an active role, shaping the discourses on cyber security via white papers and regulation and advocacy. This national and international AI regulation then, in effect, determines the visibility of such discourses. To build upon this point is the Floridi's (2020) idea of digital sovereignty, which provides grounds to analyze how nations control their digital infrastructure and how policies shape the data storage. The EU AI acts, China's state-controlled model, and an extent of BRICS + commitment to sovereign cloud infrastructure are some manifestations of the highly diverse ways that AI-induced cyber security can be contained within a framework. While Google, Microsoft, and Huawei push their own models of governance, they are often at odds with national ones, making enforcement of

Table 1
Digital Governance Concept Distribution in 2024 Digital Defense Reports of Leading Tech Global Companies

	Alphabet 2024 Gr=699	IBM 2024 Gr=104	Meta 2024 Gr=306	Microsoft 2024 Gr=2371	Total
Action Gr=112	23	18	18	53	112
Activity Gr=120	40	2	8	70	120
Actor Gr=173	3	0	0	170	173
AI Gr=430	63	55	18	294	430
Asset Gr=89	61	1	5	22	89
Attack Gr=185	8	0	0	177	185
Business Gr=195	117	9	33	36	195
Cybersecurity Gr=182	12	3	0	167	182
Data Gr=322	46	24	147	105	322
Expense Gr=61	61	0	0	0	61
Government Gr=84	19	0	1	64	84
Identity Gr=65	0	0	0	65	65
Impact Gr=170	2	2	28	138	170
Income Gr=61	60	0	1	0	61
Investment Gr=106	84	4	6	12	106
Law Gr=88	60	1	4	23	88
Liability Gr=55	55	0	0	0	55
Management Gr=84	35	9	14	26	84
Operation Gr=204	51	3	46	104	204
Product Gr=157	116	4	13	24	157
Revenue Gr=127	118	6	2	1	127
Risk Gr=170	59	5	24	82	170

Security Gr=414	89	6	2	317	414
Service Gr=231	130	4	4	93	231
System Gr=163	26	2	19	116	163
Threat Gr=304	8	0	1	295	304
User Gr=161	75	1	0	85	161
Value Gr=120	72	18	23	7	120
Total	1493	177	417	2546	4633

Clearly, “data” (n = 322) was mentioned most often across the companies considered (Table 1), thus emphasizing data's importance in digital sovereignty as both a strategic resource and an area of contention (Floridi, 2020). As the leader in contributions, Microsoft used “impact” (n = 138), “system” (n = 116), and “actor” (n = 170) to refer to systemic threats in cybersecurity from a diverse array of state and non-state actors, as well as AI system insertion into national infrastructure and global infrastructure. The “service” (n = 130), “revenue” (n = 118), and “business” (n = 117) referents from Alphabet demonstrate a frame of AI solutions that is intensely commercialized and platform-centric in alignment with Innovation Systems Theory (Fagerberg, 2005), which relates technological development to global competitiveness. High use of “data” (n = 147) and “operation” (n = 46) signals that Meta focuses on operational infrastructure, while IBM, which has the lowest total contribution across the companies (n = 95) focused quite narrowly on “data” (n = 24) and “value” (n = 18), pointing towards a more conceptual framing concerning information's value and

governance. The exclusive “identity” proof by Microsoft and “expense” and “income” alone by Alphabet revealed divergent geopolitical narratives. Microsoft's generally reflected concerns about its focus on identity management and digital authentication in national security. On the other hand, the framing from Alphabet associated AI security with investments in economics and infrastructure, emphasizing commodification and capitalism regarding AI-based cybersecurity in a governance perspective. This analysis is based on Geopolitical Theory (Kaplan, 2012), reinforcing further evidence for the argument that the digital infrastructures promoted by these Digital Defense reports serve not as neutral technologies but as ultimate strategic influence tools. Further, this evidence strengthens the Digital Sovereignty framework within which increasingly private tech actors mediate state power and autonomy in cyberspace positioning themselves as partners and challengers of the traditional geopolitical actors.

Table 2
Geopolitical and Cybersecurity Concepts Distribution in 2024 Digital Defense Reports of Leading Tech Global Companies

	Alphabet 2024 Gr=699	IBM 2024 Gr=104	Meta 2024 Gr=306	Microsoft 2024 Gr=2371	Total
AI Gr=430	63	55	18	294	430
Attack Gr=185	8	0	0	177	185
Cybersecurity Gr=182	12	3	0	167	182

Government Gr=84	19	0	1	64	84
Law Gr=88	60	1	4	23	88
Liability Gr=55	55	0	0	0	55
Security Gr=414	89	6	2	317	414
Threat Gr=304	8	0	1	295	304
Total	314	65	26	1337	1742

Overall, the information presented reflects the frequency of keywords highlighted in 2024 Digital Defense Reports from Alphabet (n = 699), IBM (n = 104), Meta (n = 306), and Microsoft (n = 2,371) with a combined total of 1,742 occurrences across eight core concepts geopolitical and cybersecurity-related (Table 2). The mentioned keyword distribution indicates the rhetorical positions and strategic interests of each tech firm toward AI-driven cybersecurity, digital sovereignty, and regulatory landscapes.

“AI” (n = 430) was the most highlighted concept, with Microsoft (n = 294) followed by Alphabet (n = 63), IBM (n = 55), and Meta (n=18) being trailing behind. This only strengthens Microsoft’s lead in probably setting the discourse around AI in the security context. “Security” (n = 414) and “threat” (n = 304) are other concepts drawn mainly by Microsoft (n = 317 and 295, respectively), reinforcing the line of critique that suggests equating AI with national and organizational risks, thus falling within the securitization theory in international relations (Buzan et al., 1998).

“Cybersecurity” stood out at 182 occurrences altogether, with Microsoft again contributing the most (n = 167), and distantly followed by Alphabet (n = 12), suggesting a sharp contrast between their integration of cybersecurity into the corporate and geopolitical narrative between them. Unlike Microsoft, however, Alphabet has a disproportionate emphasis on “law” (n = 60) and “liability” (n = 55), which together account for more than 36% of its keyword total-alegalistic framing of digital governance. This aligns with Alphabet’s strategies for navigating regulation challenges dictated by its

position in antitrust and data compliance debates within the EU and U.S.

Microsoft too took the lead by defining “attack” (n = 177) and “government” (n = 64), reinforcing the narrative as to coordinated public-private such defense strategy and national cyber threats. Lows of “government” (n = 19) and “cybersecurity” (n = 12) further prove its more business-centric risk-averse communication.

Meta and IBM contributed marginally to the strategic cybersecurity narrative, contributing only 26 and 65 keyword instances respectively across all terms. This low participation is the manifestation of a platform and governance focus (Meta) and cybersecurity conceptual architecture (IBM) rather than a direct policy positioning or geopolitical engagement. It was mainly Alphabet that raised liability and law, central issues in the debate on accountability and regulation in AI, perhaps in anticipation of constraints or damage to its reputation. Meta and IBM hardly bothered about it. This may indicate different strategies or stakeholder interests in the governance of regulation. On the one hand, the data tell a geopolitical story of bifurcation: Microsoft’s narrative is one embracing securitization and proactive alignment with the state, while Alphabet is more concerned about legal responsibility and liability avoidance. Such competing rhetorical divergences highlight the contested terrain of digital sovereignty, signaling hopefully different visions for future global cybersecurity governance and artificial-intelligence regulation.

Table 3: Sentiment Analysis in 2024 Digital Defense Reports of Leading Tech Global Companies

	Alphabet 2024 Gr=699	IBM 2024 Gr=104	Meta 2024 Gr=306	Microsoft 2024 Gr=2371	Total
Sentiment: Negative Gr=534	173	25	52	284	534
Sentiment: Neutral Gr=772	248	30	125	369	772
Sentiment: Positive Gr=874	278	49	129	418	874
Total	699	104	306	1071	2180

The insights shared through the sentiment analysis of the 2024 Digital Defense Report of Alphabet, IBM, Meta, and Microsoft help one understand the changing geopolitical architecture above AI-supported cybersecurity and issues furthering national digital sovereignty within it (Table 3). Hence, out of the 2,180 sentiment expressions studied, an effective case of positive dominance (874) over neutral (772) and negative (534) can strongly be said to be reflecting a particular narrative strategy, moreover, in emulating the common geopolitical objectives-projection of technological leadership, trustworthiness, and strategic alignment to state as well as regulatory interests. The fact that is admitted and sealed by these corporations is that they do not merely narrate cybersecurity developments. They influence the story about global digital power by selective sentiment framing. While Microsoft remains the more prolific contributor with 1,071 sentiments, the percentages have a neat symmetry: 39% positive, 34% neutral, and 27% negative. Strange as this bias seems, it has to do with showing a case of deliberate rhetorical positioning. This balance shows the transparency as well as the strategic self-image that makes the company a geopolitical stakeholder ready to team up with states in the defense of digital border and important infrastructure. Similar results were achieved by Alphabet; about 40% is proclaimed as positive, 35% neutral, and 25% negative. As such, this doubles as technology asserts its capabilities while subtly reinforcing its image as the public trust and the globalization norms steward role consistent with the company's investments in regulatory dialogues and governance frameworks.

Meta's sentiment profile shows a major change from the previously scandal-ridden company to now becoming one of the proactive developers of globally relevant tech solutions, and at 42% in its extremely positive sentiments, whereas only 17% undo negative

ones. This sentiment skew, therefore, points to reputational recalibration and aims to secure a more favorable position for international cybersecurity governance dialogues. Despite the lesser contribution (106 sentiments), IBM exhibits the highest proportion in terms of relative positivity (47%), showing how a legacy brand tries to remain geopolitically relevant through innovation and institutional robustness in enterprise cybersecurity solutions.

Thus, where this sentiment configuration is viewed in light of Geopolitical Theory (Kaplan, 2012) and Digital Sovereignty (Floridi, 2020), it becomes evident that these white papers are not mere technical documents, but also meant to serve as instruments of soft power. Technology giants euphemistically frame AI cybersecurity initiatives in highly positive or neutral tones and negotiate their roles in shaping national and supranational digital policies. Overall, the much diminished negative sentiment (just 25%) raises the prospect of a geopolitical strategy of optimism-driven messaging, which is viewed primarily as a preemptive strategy against state regulation.

In a way sentiments are not only communicational archetypes but also political signals; that Microsoft and Alphabet use them as tactics of domination in cybersecurity narratives, to steer the discourses on digital sovereignty and ultimately mark their places in emerging architectures of global security. However, the striking silence in these reports with respect to critical reflection raises serious concerns about both the transparency and acknowledgment of risk as well as the extent to which private narratives derail or displace public-interest discussions about cybersecurity. In this sense, sentiment analysis maps not only emotional tone but also the shapes of power, influence and control within an ever-growing world governed by AI and digital infrastructure

Table 4
Coefficient Analysis in 2024 Digital Defense Reports of Leading Global Tech Companies

	Alphabet Gr=49		IBM Gr=26		Meta Gr=127		Microsoft Gr=264	
	count	coefficient	count	coefficient	count	coefficient	count	coefficient
AI Gr=430	17	0.04	16	0.04	23	0.04	139	0.25
Cybersecurity Gr=182	2	0.01	1	0.00	2	0.01	115	0.35
Security Gr=414	3	0.01	2	0.00	3	0.01	144	0.27

The keyword frequency and coefficient analysis use contrasting methodological approaches, indicating notable divergences in thematic focus and narrative force across the security defense reports for 2024 between the four giant tech firms of Alphabet, IBM, Meta, and Microsoft (Table 4). Concerning AI, Microsoft has evidently taken the lead in discussion, raising it 139 times with a strong coefficient of 0.25, which indicates both volume and emphasis on this subject. On the contrary, Alphabet, IBM, and Meta saw mentions for AI being very low at 17, 16, and 23 respectively, showing very little attention to the topic of AI and with coefficients of 0.04. This evidently illustrates that Microsoft has made AI a strategic focus, evidently as it fits with much of its recent vigorous investment in generative AI tools (e.g., Copilot, OpenAI partnerships), whereas other firms seem to be adopting a more restrained or guarded posture. Microsoft stands out once again in its strong focus on cybersecurity, with 115 mentions and a coefficient of 0.35, the highest of all companies and keywords under consideration. The other companies have hardly considered the term at all, with Alphabet bringing it up only twice, IBM once, and Meta twice, each having a coefficient between 0.00 and 0.01 that barely reflects any importance. The obvious divide is thus indicative that Microsoft has framed cybersecurity as a matter of primary concern and priority since quite some time now, perhaps due to its wider concerns of enterprise solutions and cloud infrastructure, whereby the rest of the companies would have rather subsumed the topic under their broader security narratives, or in some cases, outrightly neglected it. Once again, Microsoft leads, with 144 mentions and a coefficient of 0.27, far ahead of Alphabet (3), IBM (2), and Meta (3), each with a coefficient of 0.01 or less. Strong security

emphasis in its white papers reinforces the trust, reliability, and protection narrative in its digital ecosystem, supporting its position as a leader in enterprise-grade solutions.

Microsoft's report 2024 exhibit heavy thematic emphasis on AI, cybersecurity, and security, indicating a strategic communication alignment with public concerns and enterprise expectations, including regulatory discourse. In contrast, Alphabet, IBM, and Meta show minimal commitment to these keywords, indicating either a different strategic framing, more diffuse terminology, or lesser prominence in their public message. The values of the coefficients, particularly for Microsoft, highlight frequent mention and contextual salience, implying the deliberately situated importance assigned to these issues.

Discussion

With the findings of this study, the field has not only further developed but also undergone a critical appraisal of the past studies pertaining to AI, cybersecurity, and digital sovereignty. In affirming Floridi's (2020) conceptualization of data as the cornerstone of digital sovereignty, this research evidences that data continues to be the most heavily contested and revisited issue for all companies, corroborating its dual role as a form of commodity and a site of geopolitical contestation. While past scholarship, such as Coskuntuncel (2018) and DeNardis (2014), has approached the privatization of internet governance and cybersecurity as functions, this study extends this perspective by showing how corporate actors such as Microsoft, Alphabet, and Meta create divergent yet strategic narratives to impact each of the national and global security architectures.

Microsoft's insistence on "identity," "actor," and "system" is echoing with literature characterizing the company as a hybrid geopolitical entity (Bradshaw, S., & DeNardis, L. (2024)), which has been actively influencing cyber norms and authentication standards. In contrast, the same gesture for Alphabet is revenue-speak, where technological leadership is closely associated with dynamics of the global marketplace. Meta's discourse, focused on operations and data, resonates with earlier critiques of platform capitalism (Zuboff, 2019), proposing that security is used as a veneer to normalize surveillance infrastructures.

IBM's lexicon, both selective and conceptual, would seem to at least attempt to ensure strategic relevance through normative framing, thus paralleling the earlier findings on its repositioning in discourses around digital ethics (Crawford & Paglen, 2021). In summation, the study affirms that AI-driven cybersecurity is more than a question of technology; rather, it becomes a geopolitical discourse in which private entities negotiate, legitimize, and sometimes contest the classic state-centric account of order—an observation made by Kaplan (2012) and one which reaffirms the ever-greater blurring of lines between corporate influence and sovereign power.

The 2024 Digital Defense Reports indicate that both Microsoft and Alphabet have different strategies concerning the AI-powered cyber security. Microsoft's terms such as "security," "threat," and "attack" are based on the theory of securitization and point towards AI and cyber security being construed within the confines of national security, affirming the organization's priorities towards the defense of the US (Buzan et al., 1998; Nye, 2010). The "liability" and "law" approaches of Alphabet will be testament to its recently formulated offensive strategy against the developing regulatory pressure that it receives from the EU and the U.S. (Cath et al., 2018; Binns, 2018). In the same breath, it depicts the effort on the part of Alphabet to paint itself in legal compliance to meet up with the concerns that crop up concerning the effect of AI on society. The different places allocated to Meta and IBM underscore the techno-politics divide with Meta putting on platform governance and with IBM concentrating on cyber-security infrastructure (Topor, 2023; Petrincic & Makatura 2025). The security

versus regulation rhetoric brings in its fold all broader geopolitical tensions concerning digital sovereignty, as Microsoft, with its American base, pushes for security which will give Alphabet the challenges of navigating global legal regimes. The need to have a balanced table for AI governance concerning security and regulation arises in the ongoing debate over AI ethics and accountability around the globe (Binns, 2018; Caveltly & Leese, 2018).

Sentiment analysis of the Digital Defense Reports 2024 by the major tech players—Microsoft, Alphabet, Meta, and IBM—framed cybersecurity narratives strategically to further political ends. A striking prevalence of positive sentiment (874 of a total 2,180 expressions) mingling with active attenuation of negative sentiment (534 expressions) conforms with other studies asserting that corporations use sentiment to bolster their position and garner influence and trustworthiness (Binns, 2018; Caveltly & Leese, 2018). Such a maneuver is communicationally empowering and projects soft power since it steers the discourse towards cybersecurity and digital sovereignty.

This distribution of sentiment is carefully orchestrated by Microsoft, which finds 39% of the expressions coded positive, 34% neutral, and 27% negative. This finding is further corroborated by research on geopolitical interpretations of corporate rhetoric. Some scholars have argued that multinational corporations with ties to the government have learned to harness the discourse to put themselves forward as important partners in national defense strategies (Nye, 2010; Buzan et al., 1998). By its rhetoric, Microsoft intends not only to position itself as one of the many players in the private sector but also as a geopolitical stakeholder in the shaping of the cybersecurity landscape in partnership with states. A sentiment distribution similar to that of Alphabet (40% positive, 35% neutral, and 25% negative) indicates that it is increasingly becoming cognizant of regulatory compliance and global governance (Binns, 2018). This may be seen as a concerted effort by Alphabet to avoid the complexities of AI regulation, especially in the EU, where it has been subjected to pressure regarding privacy and antitrust matters. Earlier works have suggested that alignments of such rhetoric with

regulatory environments are a means by which tech giants avoid scrutiny while buttressing their self-assumed role in global governance (Floridi, 2020).

Positive sentiment toward Meta (42%) and low sentiment toward negativity (17%) signal a reputational shift that draws attention to its attempts to recover from past scandals and reframe its position in global cybersecurity dialogues. This goes with the strategic application of sentiment to recalibrate public perception, as investigated in the literature concerning corporate reputation management (Petrinec & Makatura 2025).

Last, the positive sentiment expressed toward IBM relative to others (47%) indicates the company's desire to remain public within the current geopolitics, maintaining its focus on enterprise cybersecurity innovation. Such sentiment suggests IBM as a strategically reliable actor, well-grounded in institutional legitimacy, within a space increasingly dominated by younger tech giants. The critical insights produced by this analysis of sentiments suggest a strategic positioning of sentiment analysis itself but raise doubts about an apparently concurrent lack of negative sentiment. Reports can also be criticized for not reflecting critically on the risks and moral concerns raised by AI in the realm of cybersecurity; this gives credence, again, to criticisms of corporate self-regulation that tend to silence wider debates in the public interest. Messages on corporate accountability (Firoozi & Ku, 2023) caution that this very commercial optimism may backfire and create an image with a positive spin that plays down the dangers of AI while avoiding discussions regarding data privacy, discrimination, and AI bias. This necessitates a more transparent, balanced exchange emphasizing the public good, as opposed to corporate interests, in matters relating to AI governance and digital sovereignty.

In the 2024 Digital Defense Reports, the frequency and coefficient analysis of AI, cybersecurity, and security among Alphabet, IBM, Meta, and Microsoft point to Microsoft's entrenched positioning of AI and cybersecurity as key strategic priorities. High emphasis on Microsoft (139 AI mentions, 115 cybersecurity, and 144 security) in the security reports with the coefficient range of 0.25-0.35 is quite consistent with previous research related to Microsoft's attempt to position itself as a leader in

AI-driven enterprise solutions and national cybersecurity (Nye, 2010; Buzan et al., 1998). Microsoft is also perceiving its programmatic dialogue around these keywords as a means to exert influence on the regulatory frameworks for positioning itself as an important national security and digital sovereignty player.

But with low exposure of these concepts (coefficients near 0.01), there lies a different strategic approach that probably embeds AI and cybersecurity into a wider picture or deem them lesser than intermediary issues such as legal governance or platform integrity. This distinction agrees with studies on corporate discourse arguing that firms adapt their messaging based on market role and geopolitical position (Binns 2018; Floridi 2020). Microsoft's strong emphasis on these keywords reflects not only market leadership but also a strategy to tie in national security agendas, which may eclipse other more regulatory narratives perhaps initiated by Alphabet or similar.

Conclusion

Consequently, in the analysis of the 2024 Digital Defense Reports published by Microsoft, Alphabet, Meta, and IBM, they emphasize the strategic placement of corporate narratives in shaping the discourse around AI-driven cybersecurity and digital sovereignty. Thus, the findings reaffirm myriad existing literature surrounding the privatization of cybersecurity governance and the hybrid geopolitical roles played by the major tech companies in general, and Microsoft, in particular. One can argue that Microsoft's pronounced concern with AI, cybersecurity, and security is indicative of its attempt to be recognized as a geopolitical player trying to legitimize itself with national defense agendas and to assert its role in shaping the emerging global security architecture. Conversely, the regulatory focus from Alphabet indicates its quest for maneuverability within different global governance frameworks, particularly in the European Union, while Meta and IBM stand on the sidelines, focusing on governance on the platform and enterprise-rooted cybersecurity. Undeniably, the sentiment analysis reveals a variable degree of positive sentiment as a tool for intervention, corroborating previously stated research about corporate soft power to project status

and authority. Yet another troubling instance is that while these reports have all failed to reflect upon the dangers and ethical concerns of applying AI to cybersecurity, the companies' self-regulatory transparency is made suspect by their refutations of negative sentiments. Instead, the corporations push away the scrutiny of some topics crucial for public-interest debate such as data privacy, discrimination, bias in AI, among others.

Recommendations

This study thus creates a clear demand for a more balanced and transparent dialogue about AI governance that clearly favors end-user interest over corporation interest. Considering the ever-changing narratives that technology giants create over global cybersecurity, it is very important to ensure that their influence is put under scrutiny and accountability, as a safeguard against ill-consolidation of digital sovereignty within private hands.

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